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Factors associated with early apical peri-implantitis: A retrospective study covering a 20-year period

KEY WORDS

early apical peri-implantitis, implant failure, implant periapical lesion, retrograde peri-implantitis

ABSTRACT

Purpose: To explore risk indicators potentially associated with early apical peri-implantitis (EAP).

Materials and methods: A retrospective survey was performed in 2017 recording information from patients receiving dental implants between 1996 and 2016. Reporting follows the STROBE (strengthening the reporting of observational studies in epidemiology) guidelines. Data were collected from the medical histories and radiographs: diagnosis of EAP (health/disease), gender, age, type of surgery (immediate/delayed placement), implants placed (position, width, length, location, mesial and distal tooth-implant distance measured at the apex, state of the adjacent tooth and tooth being replaced, and surgical complications. Once the EAP had developed, data were collected regarding days of evolution, symptoms, signs and radiological findings.

Results: A total of 2548 patients (57.1% females and 42.9% males) with 8110 implants were enrolled in the study. 46 patients with 58 implants were diagnosed with EAP – 23 in the maxilla (39.6%) and 35 in the mandible (60.4%) – between 6 and 50 days after implant placement, with a mean period of 21.7 days (SD 10.1). The frequency of EAP was 1.81% in patients and 0.71% in implants. Immediate placement multiplied the odds of developing EAP 21-fold (95% CI 6.74 – 65.7; $P < 0.001$) versus delayed placement. The existence of an apical lesion in the tooth being replaced multiplied the odds of developing EAP 26.3-fold (95% CI 4.24 – 162.8; $P < 0.001$). Replacing a tooth endodontically treated increased the odds 3.48 times (95% CI 0.99 – 12.3; $P = 0.052$). The presence of an adjacent endodontically treated tooth increased the odds 0.97-fold (95% CI 0.26 – 3.60; $P = 0.963$). An apical mesial distance of ≤ 1.5 mm increased the odds up to 5.12-fold (95% CI 2.12 – 12.4; $P < 0.001$).

Conclusions: The presence of endodontic periapical lesions or endodontic treatment in the tooth being replaced, immediate implant placement or mesial tooth-implant distance measured at the apex were significantly associated with increased odds of EAP.

Conflict of interest statement: *The authors declare no conflicts of interest in relation to this study.*

*First and second authors claim for equal authorship.

Introduction

Early apical peri-implantitis (EAP), also known as an implant periapical lesion, is an infectious and inflammatory process of the tissues surrounding the implant apex. The coronal bone architecture

may be preserved during the early stages of the process, though with the risk of progression towards osseointegration failure¹.

The biological failure of dental implants is divided into early (failure to establish osseointegration) and late (failure to maintain established

Fig 1 Study flow-chart.

osseointegration)². EAP constitutes early failure, since the osseointegration process is interrupted, and is diagnosed between 7 days and 3 months after implant placement³⁻⁹. The diagnosis of EAP is based on the clinical and radiographic findings. Clinically, EAP is characterised by symptoms (pain and tightness) and signs (swelling, fistula and drainage) of variable intensity, depending on the stage of the lesion. Radiographically, a radiolucency around the implant apex may be observed⁶.

EAP is infrequent, with a reported incidence of 0.26 to 7.8%^{3,4,7,8}. Few publications involve large samples ($n \geq 10$), and there is a lack of homogeneity regarding the criteria used to diagnose the disease. The existing evidence in this regard remains limited. In view of the characteristics of the onset of EAP, it proves difficult to obtain previously recorded information on the state of the adjacent teeth and of the tooth being replaced. Furthermore, it is difficult to compile data on the timing of implant placement with a view to identifying the risk of pre-existing disease, or to establish the risk of EAP in the course of the surgical implant placement procedure.

Different etiological factors have been suggested, based on the potential source of contamination: disturbance of the surgical bed (implant surface contamination^{9,10} or overheating during drilling^{9,11}); pre-existing disease; immediate post-extraction placement⁴; endodontic disease associated with the extracted tooth or adjacent teeth^{3,12,13}; pre-existing bone disease^{3,14,15}; and the presence of root remains or foreign bodies^{9,16}. The body of evidence is very limited, however. At present, EAP is considered to

have a multifactorial origin, involving the exposure to one or more triggering factors.

The present study was carried out to explore risk indicators that may be related to the development of EAP.

Materials and methods

Study design

A retrospective chart review was performed in 2017 in the Department of Oral Surgery, at the Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry, University of Valencia, Valencia, Spain, following the STROBE (strengthening the reporting of observational studies in epidemiology) statement¹⁷ and recording information from patients receiving dental implants between 1996 and 2016 (Fig 1). All patients signed the corresponding informed consent form, and the study design was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Valencia (H1478255958653).

Sample selection

Eligibility criteria

Two groups were established according to the diagnosis of EAP: test group (patients diagnosed with EAP) and control group (patients with osseointegrated implants showing no inflammatory/infectious process).

The following inclusion criteria were applied: patients ≥ 18 years of age and with controlled medical conditions who received implant treatment. For

the test group, the following additional inclusion criteria were used: symptoms and signs suggesting EAP after implant placement; the absence of implant mobility; dull percussion of non-submerged implants; and the presence or absence of an apical radiolucency. The follow-up of the control group was up to implant loading. Since it is a pathology that appears during the period of osseointegration, it was considered a sufficient follow-up in the control group to have overcome this period.

Patients with implants placed using guided bone regeneration were excluded in both groups, since infection of the material is clinically similar to EAP and could be a bias for the results.

Data collection

The following variables were compiled in a first database (Numbers, Apple, Cupertino, CA, USA) from the medical histories and radiographs of all patients by a blinded examiner (JBT): gender; age; type of surgery (immediate/delayed placement); implants placed (position, width, length); location; mesial and distal tooth-implant distance measured at the apex (in mm, and divided into ≤ 1.5 mm and > 1.5 mm) (Fig 2); apical lesion or endodontic treatment in the tooth being replaced or adjacent endodontically treated tooth; and surgical complications. The following additional variables were collected in those cases that developed EAP: days of evolution; symptoms; signs; and radiological findings.

Intraoral radiographs (VistaScan, Dürr Dental, Bietigheim-Bissingen, Germany) and cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) scans (Planmeca Promax Mid, Roselle, IL, USA) were used to diagnose implant periapical lesions. The CBCT images were visualised using Planmeca Romexis software on a 21.5-inch monitor (iMac, Apple). Radiographs were taken using a parallelisation method with a Rinn XCP Ring positioner (Dentsply, Constanz, Germany). The measurement of distances on the intra-oral radiographs was performed with DBSWIN Imaging Software (Dürr Dental).

Statistical analysis

A biostatistician with expertise in dentistry analysed

Fig 2 Illustration of the radiographical measurements. Distances were measured rectangular to the long axis of the adjacent tooth mesially and distally.

all the data using the SPSS version 21 for Macintosh (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA).

The gender, age, type of surgery (immediate/delayed placement), implants placed (position, width, length), location, mesial and distal tooth-implant distance measured at the apex, apical lesion or endodontic treatment in the tooth being replaced or adjacent endodontically treated tooth and surgical complications were analysed. In those cases that developed EAP: days of evolution, symptoms, signs, and radiological findings were also registered. A descriptive analysis was performed for these variables (mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum, and median for continuous parameters, and absolute and relative frequencies for categorical parameters). The impact or degree of association between a predictive factor and the diagnosis was estimated by means of the odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence interval (95% CI), using the Wald chi-squared statistical test.

A multi-level binary logistic regression using generalised estimation equations was applied to obtain adjusted OR and to control within-patient dependence of implants. This model estimated usual beta coefficients and Wald statistic was calculated as $(\text{beta}/\text{s.e.})^2$, where s.e. was the standard error for beta. Wald Chi-square was used to calculate confidence intervals. The 95% confidence intervals for beta were calculated as usual $(\text{beta} \pm 1.96 \times \text{s.e.})$ and transformed to exponentials $e^{\text{beta} \pm 1.96 \times \text{s.e.}}$. The level of statistical significance was defined as 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Table 1 Distribution according to location and arch of the controls and cases of early apical peri-implantitis

Arch	Location	Total		Control Group		Early apical peri-implantitis group	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Total	Total	8110	100.0%	8052	99.3%	58	0.7%
	Incisors	1594	100.0%	1574	98.7%	20	1.3%
	Canines	500	100.0%	490	98.0%	10	2.0%
	Premolars	2686	100.0%	2663	99.1%	23	0.9%
	Molars	3330	100.0%	3325	99.8%	5	0.2%
Maxillary	Total	3660	100.0%	3637	99.4%	23	0.6%
	Incisors	675	100.0%	668	99.0%	7	1.0%
	Canines	211	100.0%	206	97.6%	5	2.4%
	Premolars	1002	100.0%	993	99.1%	9	0.9%
	Molars	1772	100.0%	1770	99.9%	2	0.1%
Mandible	Total	4450	100.0%	4415	99.2%	35	0.8%
	Incisors	919	100.0%	906	98.6%	13	1.4%
	Canines	289	100.0%	284	98.3%	5	1.7%
	Premolars	1684	100.0%	1670	99.2%	14	0.8%
	Molars	1558	100.0%	1555	99.8%	3	0.2%

Results

A retrospective study was carried out in 2548 patients (42.9% males and 57.1% females; mean age 59.2 years (SD 12.1), range 20 to 94) with 8110 implants in the period between 1996 and 2016.

Data in the control group were collected from 8052 dental implants: 3637 in the maxilla (45.2%) and 4415 in the mandible (54.8%). Data in the test group were collected from 58 implants in 46 patients that developed EAP: 32 women (69.6%) and 14 men (30.4%), with a mean age of 51.9 years (SD 11.9) (range 26 to 75). The implant locations in both groups are described in Table 1.

With regard to the timing of implant placement, in the control group a total of 400 implants were placed immediately after extraction (4.9%) while 7652 were placed in healed sites (95.1%). In the test group, 35 implants were placed immediately after extraction (60.3%) while 23 implants were placed in healed sites (39.7%). EAP was diagnosed in 8% of the immediate implants versus 0.3% of the delayed placement implants (Fig 3). Immediate placement multiplied the odds of developing EAP 21-fold (95% CI 6.74 – 65.7; $P < 0.001$) versus delayed placement (Table 2).

In the control group, in 6923 locations, there was no apical lesion in the tooth being replaced (85.9%); in 84 cases the tooth presented an apical lesion (1.1%); in 491 cases the tooth being replaced had undergone endodontic treatment with no apical lesion (6.1%); and in 554 cases the adjacent teeth were endodontically treated (6.9%), with no apical lesion.

In the test group, in 29 cases the tooth being replaced showed no endodontic apical lesion (50%); in 10 cases the tooth being replaced presented an apical lesion at the time of extraction (17.2%); in 15 cases the tooth being replaced had undergone endodontic treatment (25.9%); and in four cases the adjacent teeth were endodontically treated, with no apical lesion (6.9%).

EAP was diagnosed in 11.1% of the implants replacing teeth with endodontic apical lesions; in 3% when the previous tooth had undergone endodontic treatment; and in 0.7% when the implants had an adjacent tooth subjected to endodontic treatment (Fig 4). If the tooth being replaced had an apical lesion, the odds of developing EAP was multiplied 26.3-fold (95% CI 4.24 – 162.8; $P < 0.001$); if the tooth being replaced had been endodontically treated, the odds increased 3.48-fold (95% CI 0.99 – 12.3; $P = 0.052$); and if the

Fig 3 Early apical peri-implantitis according to implant placement.

Fig 4 Early apical peri-implantitis according to the site of implant placement.

Table 2 Association between injury (no/yes) and independent factors: results multi-level logistic regression models with generalised estimation equations (EEG)

Factors	Non adjusted odds ratio (OR)			Adjusted odds ratio (OR)		
	OR	95% CI	P value	OR	95% CI	P value
Timing implant placement (delayed) immediate	29.1	15.8 – 53.7	< 0.001***	21.0	6.74 – 65.7	< 0.001***
Site of implant placement (no lesion)			< 0.001***			0.002***
Lesion in tooth being replaced	29.9	13.7 – 65.2	< 0.001***	26.3	4.24 – 162.8	< 0.001***
Endodontic treatment in tooth being replaced	7.31	3.69 – 14.5	< 0.001***	3.48	0.99 – 12.3	0.052
Endodontically treated adjacent teeth	1.73	0.58 – 5.13	0.325	0.97	0.26 – 3.60	0.963
Apical mesial distance (> 1.5 mm) ≤ 1.5 mm	6.1	2.64 – 13.8	< 0.001***	5.12	2.12 – 12.4	< 0.001***
Apical distance (> 1.5 mm) ≤ 1.5 mm	1.59	0.36 – 6.93	0.539	–	–	–

*P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Non adjusted/adjusted odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence interval (CI).

adjacent tooth had been endodontically treated, the odds increased 0.97-fold (95% CI 0.26 – 3.60). No statistically significant differences were found (P = 0.963) (Table 2).

In the control group we were able to measure the mesial distance between the adjacent teeth and the implant in 2869 implants: in 2557 cases the distance was > 1.5 mm (89.1%), while in 312 cases the distance was ≤ 1.5 mm to the apex of the adjacent tooth (10.9%). In 1687 implants we were able to measure the distal distance: 1576 cases presented a distance > 1.5 mm (93.4%), while in 111 cases the distance was ≤ 1.5 mm (6.6%). In the test group, 24 implants had an adjacent mesial tooth with a mean apical distance of 1.76 mm (SD 0.72) (Table 3). When the recommended mesial distance (≤ 1.5 mm) was not respected, the EAP rate was 3.2% (n = 10), versus 0.5% (n = 14) when the distance was respected (> 1.5 mm). 20

implants had an adjacent distal tooth with a mean distance of 2.59 mm (SD 0.86). When the distal distance was not respected, the EAP rate was 1.8% (n = 2), versus 1.1% (n = 18) when the distance was respected (Fig 5). An apical mesial distance ≤ 1.5 mm raised the odds up to 5.12-fold (95% CI 2.12 – 12.4; P < 0.001). There were no significant differences in the distal distances (P = 0.539) (Table 2).

The incidence of EAP in the population studied was 1.81% in patients (95% CI 1.29% – 2.32%) and 0.71% in implants (95% CI 0.53% – 0.90%) (Table 1). The diagnosis was established between 6 and 50 days after implant placement, with a mean period of 21.7 days (SD 10.1) (Fig 6). Regarding the clinical manifestations, 50 cases of EAP (86.2%) were associated with pain. Signs of inflammation developed in all 58 cases (100%), and 22 implants presented suppuration (37.9%).

Table 3 Mesial and distal tooth-implant distance measured at the apex in implants and in early apical peri-implantitis

	Apical mesial distance		Apical distal distance	
	n	mm (mean ± SD)	n	mm (mean ± SD)
Implants reviewed	2869	2.77 ± 1.30	1687	3.31 ± 1.67
≤ 1.5 mm	312 (10.9%)		111(6.6%)	
> 1.5 mm	2557 (89.1%)		1576 (93.4%)	
Early apical peri-implantitis	24	1.76 ± 0.72	20	2.59 ± 0.86
≤ 1.5 mm	10 (41.7%)		2 (10%)	
> 1.5 mm	14 (58.3%)		18 (90%)	

Fig 6 Timing of diagnosis.

Radiographically, 41 cases of EAP showed radiolucent images (70.7%).

The following parameters were significantly associated with increased odds of EAP:

- Immediate implant placement (OR = 21.0, 95% CI 6.74 – 65.7; $P < 0.001$);
- Endodontic apical lesion (OR = 26.3, 95% CI = 4.24 – 162.8; $P < 0.001$) and endodontic treatment of the tooth being replaced (OR = 3.48, 95% CI = 0.99 – 12.3; $P = 0.052$);
- Mesial distance to adjacent tooth ≤ 1.5 mm (OR = 5.12, 95% CI = 2.12 – 12.4; $P < 0.001$).

Discussion

The present paper reports a series of 58 cases of EAP. The aim of the study was to analyse the indicators potentially associated with the development of EAP.

Three studies involving samples of more than 10 implants have described the timing of detection

of the disorder. Stavaru et al¹⁸ [Ref 18 is Marinescu et al] diagnosed EAP between 1 month and 3 years after implant placement (mean 12.5 months); Quiryren et al⁸ diagnosed EAP between 2 weeks and 3 months; and Peñarrocha-Diago et al⁴ between 6 days and 2 months after implant placement (mean 18 days). Our results are consistent with the above studies, with a diagnosis of EAP between 6 and 50 days after implant placement (mean 21.7 days).

Only three studies¹⁹⁻²¹ related EAP to the timing of implant placement after dental extraction, though none reported the corresponding odds increment. They concluded that immediate implant placement in sites with previous periapical lesions can be a successful treatment modality, provided careful debridement of the extraction socket is performed. Zhao et al²², in a meta-analysis, compared immediate dental implant placement into infected versus non-infected sockets. The results suggested that immediate placement of an implant into an infected site can increase the risk of implant failure.

In our study, immediate placement multiplied the odds of developing EAP 21-fold versus delayed placement ($P < 0.001$).

With regard to endodontic treatment of an adjacent tooth or of the tooth being replaced, Lefever et al¹² concluded that when endodontic disease is present at the time of extraction, the implant is 7-fold more likely to develop EAP. In turn, when periapical disease is present in the adjacent teeth, the risk of developing EAP is likewise increased. Our findings are consistent with this study, showing a 3.48-fold increase in odds ($P < 0.001$) in the presence of a tooth that has undergone endodontic treatment.

Taking into account the tooth-implant distance and endodontic treatment, Zhou et al³ observed a statistically significant tendency to develop EAP after analysing 128 implants with endodontically treated adjacent teeth with regard to the time of implant insertion after endodontic therapy ($P < 0.05$). The distance described between the implant and the adjacent teeth was 2.99 ± 1.4 mm. In the present study, the presence of an endodontically treated adjacent tooth raised the odds of EAP up to 0.97-fold, though statistical significance was not reached ($P = 0.963$). The distance between the implant and the mesial and distal adjacent teeth was 1.76 ± 0.72 mm and 2.59 ± 0.86 mm, respectively. A mesial distance < 1.5 mm raised the odds of EAP up to 5.12-fold ($P < 0.001$), while no significant results were obtained in the case of distal distance ($P = 0.539$).

With respect to the tooth-implant distance measured at the apex, the mean mesial and distal distances between implant and tooth measured at the apex were 2.78 mm and 3.35 mm respectively, while the mean values for implants with EAP were 1.76 mm in apical mesial distance versus 2.59 mm in apical distal distance. Apical proximity to the adjacent tooth favours such lesions. In our study, the mesial apical distances were smaller than the distal distances, and this may be due to two factors: the natural curvature of the apexes towards distal; and the tendency of the operator to place the implant more mesial in the edentulous area. According to the literature^{23,24}, the root apex deviation in distal direction increases progressively from

the incisor to the canine, progressively decreasing towards the multi-radicular elements. Regarding the factors that make the ideal trajectory modify, have been described the experience of the surgeon, intentional angulation to avoid anatomical structures, small interarch distance and intra-operative discomfort^{25,26}.

Three studies have described the frequency of these lesions. Reiser et al⁷ placed 3800 implants and reported 10 cases of EAP – the incidence being 0.26%. In a retrospective study, Peñarrocha-Diago et al²⁷ diagnosed 22 cases of EAP in 5200 implants, with an incidence of 0.4%. In another retrospective study, Quirynen et al⁸ evaluated 539 implants and recorded an EAP rate of 1.6% in the maxilla versus 2.7% in the mandible. Our study obtained results similar to those published by Quirynen et al⁸, with an incidence of EAP of 1.81% in patients and 0.71% in implants. Early apical peri-implantitis produces pain, inflammation or sometimes pus, and requires adequate diagnosis and treatment. Early implant failures described in the literature possibly include undiagnosed lesions of this kind; it is therefore important to know the magnitude of their presence and their clinical management for the benefit of the patient and for avoiding removal of the implant.

Blaya-Tárraga et al²⁸ in a recent systematic review analysed 36 studies, with 15461 implants evaluated and 183 periapical implant lesions. Eight of those papers included more than five cases and 28 included equal or less than five cases. This study included a large sample of patients treated with dental implants with detailed clinical and radiographic information.

The possible sources of bias in this long-term study conducted at the university are the multiple practitioners and the change of implant systems. To minimise the risk of bias in process quality, only one trained operator collected all the variables with a strict protocol. In this study, nine different implant systems were registered (Straumann, Biomet 3i, Zimmer, Nobel Biocare, Phibo, Sweden & Martina, GMI, Mozo-Grau and Euroteknika), however, the relationship between the type of implant and its surface with the development of the EAP was not studied.

There are few publications on EAP involving large patient samples, and the existing studies have been conducted in the university clinic setting, where a large number of implants are placed and the different variables are recorded on a protocolised basis.

Conclusions

The presence of an endodontic periapical lesion or endodontic treatment in the tooth being replaced, immediate implant placement, and the apical mesial distance to the adjacent tooth were significantly associated with an increased odds of EAP.

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